

Task Modeling for User Interface Design: A Layered Approach

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Abstract—The model-based approach to user interface design relies on developing separate models that are capturing various aspects about users, tasks, application domain, presentation and dialog representations. This paper presents a task modeling approach for user interface design and aims at exploring the mappings between task, domain and presentation models. The basic idea of our approach is to identify typical configurations in task and domain models and to investigate how they relate each other. A special emphasis is put on application-specific functions and mappings between domain objects and operational task structures. In this respect, we will distinguish between three layers in the task decomposition: a functional layer, a planning layer, and an operational layer.

Keywords—task modeling, user interface design, unit tasks, basic tasks, operational task model

I. INTRODUCTION

MODEL-based approaches to user interface design are creating a promising framework for the development of interactive systems able to run in different contexts of use. Rather than starting from scratch, this approach makes it possible to develop separate models, which are capturing context variations, and to manipulate them in order to migrate from one context to another.

Models are used to capture design knowledge needed for the construction of the future user interface (UI). Main concepts abstracted into these models refer to users, tasks, application domain, presentation and dialog. User, task and domain models may be termed as contributing models since they are influencing the UI design process. In this respect, they are used for the derivation of presentation and dialog models. Model-based approaches, which are giving the task model a leading role among the other models, are also referred to as task-based approaches.

A key ingredient to the success of model-based approaches is the mapping problem related to the handling of relationships between models throughout the development life

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cycle. These relationships or mappings are of particular importance when we want to run a target application in different contexts of use while preserving usability.

According to the ISO 9241-11:1998 standard [6], usability is defined as the extent to which a product could be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction in a specified context of use. In the same standard, the context of use is defined by users, tasks, equipment (hardware, software and materials), and the physical and social environments in which a product is used. Since usability is evaluated in context, it is important for designers to rely on a flexible task representation, able to capture context variations.

Several approaches to task modeling have been proposed that are aiming to answer the needs for developing context-sensitive user interfaces. Most of them are addressing the mappings between task and platform models, such as [14] and [15], in order to build user interfaces that are preserving usability along a wide range of computer devices. In this respect they are complementary to other approaches developed in the past (see, for example [1] and [11]) aiming at the derivation of user interfaces from domain models.

This aims at presenting a layered approach to task modeling in the framework of model-based design of user interfaces. We will address the mapping problem as a rationale for the proposed task model structure. The basic idea of our approach is to identify typical configurations in both task and domain models, to investigate how they relate each other and how these configurations could be used for the design of user interfaces.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. In section II, we will discuss some related work with a focus on the mapping problem. In section III, we will briefly discuss some application-domain concepts in order to investigate the relation between application functions, tasks and domain objects. Then we will describe our task modelling framework and discuss its benefits for user interface design. The paper ends with conclusion in section V.

II. RELATED WORK

The mapping problem has been defined in [10] as a key problem for the gradual transformation of models from abstract to concrete level as well as for the mapping on the same level of abstraction. Previous work in this area highlights the concern for preserving consistency between models along the progression from one model to another [3],

elaboration of graceful degradation rules for multi-target user interfaces [5] as well as development of a description language and tools supporting the specification transitions [8].

A problem with the mapping between models is that they require a detailed representation of model components along the development process. This means that we need to consider at least three aspects when exploring the mapping space: (a) the model type (e.g. domain, task, presentation, and platform); (b) the hierarchical structure of each model (e.g. dialog unit, interaction object), and (c) the progression level along the development life cycle. Up to now, only interface models have defined transitions from abstract to final representations of the design.

The last two dimensions seem to be most neglected in existing approaches. The problems are mainly located in task and domain models since it is not clear how they relate each other and which are the transitions they have to undergo in order to effectively support the design process.

TABLE I
 TASK CATEGORIES IN CTTE

Abstract	Interaction	Application	User	Cooperative

Another important problem in model-based approaches is the tools needed to assist designers in building models and handling mappings. In order to handle relationships between models a compatibility between representations is required.

The Concur Task Tree Notation (CTT) has been implemented in the CTT Environment (CTTE) [9], which is providing with a graphical notation for task representation (see Table 1) and temporal operators (see Table 2).

There are some restrictions in combining binary and unary operators. For example, the combination $T1^{*}>>T2$ is not allowed, since $T2$ will be never performed. Also, optional tasks are not allowed in the left and right side of the operators $[>$, $[>$ and $[]$.

CTTE enables the designer to create task trees and to specify task properties such as task type, frequency, and estimated execution time. An important feature is the XML output capability that makes CTTE a useful tool for the handling of mappings between the task model and other

models.

TABLE II
 TEMPORAL OPERATORS IN CTTE

<i>Binary operators</i>	
Choice	$T1 [] T2$
Order independency	$T1 = T2$
Interleaving	$T1 T2$
Synchronization	$T1 [[]] T2$
Enabling	$T1 >> T2$
Enabling with info passing	$T1 []>> T2$
Disabling	$T1 [> T2$
Suspend / resume	$T1 [> T2$
<i>Unary operators</i>	
Optional	$[T1]$
Iteration	$T1^*$

The temporal priority (from higher to lower) is given below:

$$[] , |= , || , [[]] , [> \text{ and } [> , >> , []>>$$

CTT notation has been integrated in Teresa [10], a task-based design tool offering facilities for the computer-aided design of UIs.

III. THE APPLICATION DOMAIN MODEL

A. Application functions

The application domain model also referred to as domain model or concepts model defines the concepts related to the domain of the target application. Two components have a particular importance for the user interface design: the application functions and data model. Each function corresponds to a business goal, which is accomplished by carrying on one or several user tasks.

This mapping is often neglected in the development of interactive systems, although it provides with an important bridge between software engineering and human-computer interaction.

In order to present our work we will use an example. The purpose of the application is the management of data about products, clients and orders in a trade company. The mapping could be expressed as a task model represented in Figure 1 by using the CTT graphical notation.

Fig. 1 Mapping of application functions onto user tasks

Only high level tasks are represented in Figure 1 Tasks on the first level of decomposition correspond to business goals.

They are further decomposed in user tasks required to accomplish these goals. Since the representation in Figure 1 is mapping application functions onto user tasks, we will term it

as the functional layer of the task model.

This mapping is producing the initial representation of tasks that are relevant for the target application. For the sake of simplicity, we will focus on the task “New order” represented in Fig. 3. The task goal is to record new orders submitted by clients.

A. The Data model

The data model is capturing representations of domain objects (entities), relationships between domain objects and domain object attributes. The conceptual data model is depicted in Figure 2 according to an entity-relationship-attribute (ERA) formalism produced by the DB-MAIN tool [4]. This formalism has been chosen for its expressiveness in representing relations and its capabilities to output both a SQL and XML specifications of the model.

As pointed out by Thevenin and Coutaz [14], the domain concepts could be ranked upon the degree of importance for the application domain and the centrality for the user task. For example, the order, client and product are central entities for the task „Record orders”.

Fig. 2 The conceptual data model

In turn, the centrality of objects is determining the centrality of relationships and roles. Central relationships are the relations a central object has with other objects in a task. In order to have a complete mental model, it is important for the user to understand the relationship between domain objects. In this respect, the user should perceive all products which have been specified in an order (perceiving the 1-N relationship) in order to have a feedback on task completion. In a similar vein, it is useful to visualize the client data (perceiving of the 1-1 relationship) in order to be sure that a customer has been specified.

A binary relation has two roles and each role has its own cardinality expressed as an interval (e.g. 0-1 or 1-N). The relevant cardinality is different and depends on the centrality of the object responsible for that role. For example, the relevant role in the relation « Sending » is « sent-by », denoting that an order is sent by only one client. Similarly, in the « Ordering » relation the relevant role is « orders » with the cardinality 1: N, meaning that several products are requested by an order.

As it was pointed out in [12], cardinality of roles is important since it reveals repetitive tasks and helps in task

decomposition. Two examples are represented in Figure 3:

- The task „Record order”, which is explicitly, started by the task “Take order” (in a work session we might have no order).
- The task “Product data”, which is implicitly started (an order should specify at least one product).

A task enables the user to perform operations on domain objects. The operations may be performed at collection level (create new objects, delete or associate existing objects) or object level (modify the object attributes). The data model elements are selected according to task goals. In this respect, tasks are filtering the data model elements that are further needed for the user interface design.

IV. THE LAYERED TASK MODEL

A. Layers in task decomposition

As pointed out by activity theory [7], tasks are goal driven, being performed consciously, while actions are depending on operational conditions of the task and become automatic by practice.

This distinction is important since it reveals several layers in the task structure: a functional / planning layer that does not depend on the target platform and an operational layer. However, the operational conditions are a concept that has been further refined for UI purposes [12] by addressing two kinds of variation:

- Variations in using an interaction object: different actions required to manipulate the same interaction object. In this case, the activity is driven by requirements to adjust the work, like articulator actions (e.g. scrolling a list).
- Variations in the platform used to carry on a task: the same goal could be achieved using different user interfaces. This situation corresponds to tasks that are driven by operational goals in a given context of use.

The first case corresponds to operational conditions and is beyond the scope of our task modeling approach. The second case corresponds to the operational task model layer. Therefore we will consider that the activity is also goal-driven, like for the functional and planning layers, but goals have a different relevance.

B. Criteria for task decomposition

Task modeling is an iterative process of identification and description of tasks. Several criteria could be applied for task decomposition but their relevance is varying according to the task model layer:

- Functional: tasks associated with the same business goal. This criterion applies for task decomposition at functional level for the mapping of application functions to user tasks.
- Semantic: task performing an operation onto the same domain object. This criterion is applied to separate tasks which refer to the same object or to the same operation (add new, delete) or to the same interaction method (when several methods are available to accomplish a goal). It is

relevant for both functional and operational level and helps in the identification of unit tasks.

- Task object: tasks performing operations with the same interaction object or external object. The criterion is relevant for the operational level and helps in the identification of basic tasks.
- User and work: tasks are performed by the same user (playing a given role) and are denoting a similar work (manual, interactive, communication). The criterion is mainly relevant for cooperative tasks.
- Temporal: tasks denoting specific temporal constraints (like repetitive or optional performance). The criterion is relevant for the representation of temporal constraints among tasks.

C. The planning layer

The second layer in the task model is represented in Figure 3 and shows how users are planning task performance by decomposing a task in sub-tasks and giving an ordering preference for each of them.

Fig. 3 Decomposition for the task "Record order"

Usually, this specification results from early task analysis and represents "what-to-do" knowledge. In our design framework, this layer is the result of decomposition of the functional tasks, which are represented in Figure 1. The decomposition stops at unit task level, defined by Card, Moran & Newell [2] as tasks the user really wants to perform.

The planning layer serves for the representation of procedures used to accomplish a goal. As such, they could capture context variations related to the relevance of tasks for a specified context of use, as well as for their temporal ordering.

In our example we assumed that the client is ordering products via a phone call. In this case, the client is first asked if he is an old client and remembers his id. If he doesn't remember or the search operation fails, he is asked to tell his name. If the search by name also fails, then the operator prefers to consider him a new client and to postpone the referential integrity problem with the data base. This way, the time call is not affected by misunderstanding / misspelling issues which might often occur during a phone

communication. On another hand, the operator productivity is maintained at a reasonable level.

Therefore the "Client data" task in Figure 3 has been modeled with the operators "enabling with information passing" (e.g. T1 []>>T2) and "optional" ([T]).

However, the order could be received by task. In this case, the task is no longer co-operative so the operator could clearly decide the client status. This situation is modeled like in Figure 4. In this case, only the task of editing the client address remains optional.

Fig. 4 Decomposition for the task "Client data"

Decomposition at planning level makes it possible to handle various context situations and also to provide with a task representation for each interaction method when several ways to accomplish a goal are possible (e.g. search by id vs. search by name).

D. Decomposition at operational level

The third layer represents the operational structure of unit tasks. The decomposition of a unit task stops at basic task level, which has been defined as the lowest task level that is using a single interaction object or a single external object or serves a communicational goal [12].

Basic tasks are interaction driven and represent the "how-to-do-it" knowledge, since they show how a unit task will be actually carried on, by using various interaction techniques. According to the interaction object type, we distinguish between information control and function control basic tasks.

The task model is used as a mediator for the mapping between domain and presentation models. An information control basic task is carried on by using an information control abstract interaction object (AIO) in order to access attribute data. Available commands on the target platform are mapped onto function control basic tasks in the task model and abstract interaction objects in the presentation model.

The operational structure for the unit task „Product data" is presented in Figure 5 and consists of two function control basic tasks (ok and cancel) and seven information control basic tasks. In the CTT notation, interaction objects used for data entry are represented as interaction tasks while those that only display information on the screen are represented as application tasks.

A problem with the decomposition at operational level is related to the definition of unit tasks. Unit tasks have a given relevance for the user and do not depend on a given platform. However, it is possible for a unit task to invoke the execution

of another unit tasks. For example, selecting a product from a category is a task the user really wants to perform since it makes the product specification easier. On another hand, finding a product is also a unit task having its own operational structure, like shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5 Operational structure for the unit task "Product data"

The operational task model suggests a first level grouping of AIOs. AIO groups are providing with a first level of structuring the interface. As such, they are serving as basic building blocks for the user interface design in a task-based approach.

AIO configurations are the lowest level units of the interface that have associated both a unit task goal and a temporal relation (the ordering of basic tasks).

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

A shortcoming of many approaches is that they start with the data model and not with the task model. As we shown in this paper, the task model is filtering for relevance the data model elements, which are further, needed in the design of user interfaces.

In this paper we presented a task modeling approach for user interface design. We identified three decomposition levels, which are relevant in task modeling for user interface design:

- A functional level that results from mapping application functions onto user tasks.
- A unit task level that results from the decomposition of functional tasks regardless the constraints imposed by a target hardware and software platform.
- A basic task level that results from the decomposition of unit tasks, which are, carried on by using interaction techniques available on a target platform.

We have also identified several task-domain mappings that are useful for the model-based derivation of the presentation:

- Unit tasks – domain objects: operations performed onto domain objects are modeled as unit tasks in the task model.
- Basic tasks – domain object attributes / available commands: operations performed onto domain object attributes are mapped are mapped onto information

control basic tasks while available commands on the target platform are mapped onto function control basic tasks. In turn, basic tasks are further mapped onto abstract information object in the presentation of the user interface.

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